

COMPUTER SCIENCES

SECURING MILITARY CYBERSPACE: A DETAILED ANALYSIS OF THREAT VECTORS AND STRATEGIC SOLUTIONS FOR BATTLEFIELD NETWORKS

Tanriverdiyev E.

*National Defense University of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Azerbaijan
ORCID: 0000-0002-0984-5443*

Abstract

While networked information systems are becoming the backbone of military operations, the problems of network system security increase accordingly. Battlefield networks dependent on wireless communication due to mobility have opened up a vast potential for cybersecurity attacks. This paper provides a broad overview of the key cybersecurity threats facing the military battlefield network, with an emphasis on the risks contributed by wireless communication. It further covers advanced protection mechanisms, including encryption, access control, and continuous monitoring of networks. It assesses the security impacts of some emerging technologies: SDR and CR technologies. The security recommendations are made at the end in the form of strong encryption, real-time monitoring, and adaptive architectures for cyberspace security. These recommendations would surely help in preserving the integrity of operations in the modern military environment.

Keywords: cybersecurity, military networks, battlefield networks, wireless communication, cyber threats, defense mechanisms, software-defined radio, cognitive radio.

INTRODUCTION

It also follows that military operations are becoming increasingly digital communications network-based, extending from tactical operations to higher echelons of command and control, and down to logistics. The shift towards modern globally interconnected cyberspace systems up from traditional tactical communication networks presents an unparalleled opportunity, bringing significant security challenges simultaneously. Specific to that, radio communications over the battlefield present critical vulnerabilities that adversaries could well leverage. This paper examines those cybersecurity challenges and puts forward some strategic solutions for improving the security of military cyberspace. The increasing intricacy of modern warfare, propelled by the integration of Network Centric Warfare, or simply NCW, has rendered operations evermore reliant upon real-time information sharing. Indeed, though NCW will yield substantial gains in military operations, military networks are also exposed to a range of cybersecurity threats. [1]

Modern military communication networks have transformed drastically from loosely interconnected tactical systems to highly integrated global networks—a cyberspace enabled by ever-advancing technologies, driven by the demand for near real-time data sharing, enhanced situation awareness, and expanded mission

flexibility. Conversely, however, increased connectivity results in a commensurate increase in vulnerabilities.

Legacy Tactical Networks: The military communication systems, like Combat Net Radios, have traditionally operated in the early times in segregated environments that do not support much in terms of connectivity. Due to their physical isolation, these systems are fairly secure and deploy closed-loop channels of communication. Still, they lack the flexibility and efficiency of modern communication networks. [3]

Network Centric Warfare and Global Military Networks: The integration of Network Centric Warfare and Global Military Networks initiated a new era. NCW is based on the integration of various sub-networks wherein information is shared among operational domains in real time. This transition has also resulted in the establishment of global cyberspace related to military activities, where information is exchanged among various wireless and wired communication channels. While NCW enhances battlefield efficiency, it also creates new threats and vectors of attack, especially within wireless environments. [2]

Modern military networks, especially those based on wireless communications, are susceptible to a lot of cyber threats. These can violate confidentiality, integrity, or availability of critical information and hence can pose a severe threat to mission success.

Pic. 1. Architecture of military tactical networks

Communication experience reveals that tactical environment is the most challenging based on the following reasons. As shown by Figure 1, outdated military tactical networks are organized around nodes and the interconnecting communication links. What it is essential to understand is that it demonstrates a much worst performance than commercial or fixed network nodes and links. The main medium of communication at tactical level is known as combat network radios, mobile nodes normally operating on TCP/IP and Long Range Radio Relay (LRR). The bandwidth capacity is relatively less than that of the commercial wireless technologies. Besides that, there are some specific demands which are most important for military equipment and are less essential in case of commercial systems. As it has emerged, this paper covers only a segment of total military systems that function in actual combat mission environments.

Wireless Communication Vulnerabilities: Wireless communication is indispensable for mobile military units, but it relates to a number of types of cyber threats by nature. Unlike wired communication, the information may intercept, jam, or even manipulate the wireless signals, especially in hostile areas. The inherent risks include:

- **Eavesdropping:** The opponent may eavesdrop on wireless communications to gather sensitive information.
- **Jamming:** Wireless signals can be disrupted, preventing military units from communicating effectively.
- **Physical Attack against the Nodes:** Most of the military nodes are physically highly vulnerable to attack, which often results in communications breakdowns.

Advanced Cyber Threats: With increasing complexity in military networks, advanced cyberattacks are posing serious threats. The key ones are:

- **Wormhole Attacks:** Through the exploitation of weak spots in wireless protocols, attackers create a

tunnel between two faraway nodes and thus reroute communication.

- **Blackhole Attacks:** Malicious nodes discard packets instead of forwarding them, causing a loss of information and interrupting processes.
- **Denial-of-Service (DoS) Attacks:** An attacker overloads network resources, making them unavailable for legitimate use.

The solution for the challenges in the battlefield wireless network can be multifold, and many methods can contribute to reducing the vulnerability not only of wireless communication but also of other weaknesses in the network. Encryption and secure protocols provide confidentiality and integrity to general communications and military communications in particular.

Advanced encryption using AES-256 and IPsec reinforcements provides a robust guard for data. In addition, secure communication protocols such as WPA3 must be implemented to keep wireless communications safe. Frequency hopping and spread-spectrum modulation techniques also can help to make the possibility of interception and jamming smaller by affecting the adversary's capability to disrupt communications. [4]

Continuous network monitoring is considered the backbone of any detection and response mechanism against cyberattacks. The use of automated IDS and anomaly detection methods would also help identify such threats before they cause serious harm. Moreover, incident response planning is the prior necessary action in order to reduce or minimize the impact of cyberattacks in real time.

These radios replace traditional military communication technologies and are known as SDR and CR. With the support of SDR and CR, these radios automatically adapt to the environment in terms of frequency and waveform settings, providing more flexibility and robustness. At the same time, it opens up a new attack surface because hackers may manipulate the software-based settings. Strict security controls should be put in place and updated regularly in case vulnerabilities in SDR or CR systems are found.

The adaptation of SDR technology means that radios can support up to different waveforms and are capable of performing a vast range of tasks depending on factors such as frequency, waveform and bandwidth. This flexibility enables the development of more elastic wireless networks in all platforms; each possess strengths and limitations contingent on certain operational characteristics.

While the use of CIPRs in militarized structures extends considerable benefits, there are some important security issues where the application of IPsec and key management is concerned. Furthermore, the new IP frame structure employs significant overhead and poses a challenge in networks especially bandwidth realize in tactical military communication in areas that utilize High Frequency (HF) radio band.

In recent military exercises, adversaries exploited vulnerabilities in wireless battlefield communication systems. These attacks demonstrated the importance of strong encryption and network segmentation to prevent eavesdropping and jamming. The use of advanced security protocols, such as WPA3, significantly reduced the risk of successful cyberattacks. [5]

CONCLUSION

The increasing use of wireless communication in the military networks on the battlefield exposes these networks to a number of cybersecurity issues. These vulnerabilities are due to the nature of wireless communication which is easier to intercept, jam, or access without permission. In so doing the amount of risk appetite already built in the system has to be well contained and planned out. This includes the use of superior means of protecting data confidentiality using encryption, controlling access to limited or no access at all to unauthorized users and taking network segmentation approaches to contain potential breaches and their effects. As well, the utilization of direct network connections and the employment of special security measures such as the monitoring of network activities is also indispensable.

The above presents that new technologies such as SDR and CR have great potentials and problems for military communications. These technologies offer more efficiency and operational effectiveness in unfavorable and variable circumstances like those of a battlefield. By means of SDR, military units can change the frequency of communications during missions to

overcome jamming while in the case of CR, communications can be conducted whereby the selection of the channel is made on-the-spot. But with these new systems, there emerges the challenge that since it is software oriented, the guidelines goes that an enemy can fight back by using the bugs or configurations to cause attacks. Hence, full cybersecurity measures including updates, scout measures, and defense forces compliance etc. should be embedded in these systems against any future occurrences. If the military battlefield network is fortified with technology especially the cybersecurity component, it makes it possible for armed forces to protect sensitive information and enhances vulnerability in the communications systems. This is very important to operational efficiencies because the absence of communication or disruption of data and vice versa in those important mission tasks may result to grievous consequences.

A comprehensive cyber defense system capable of adapting to new technologies and their corresponding threats is going to help military organizations outsmart their enemies and perform safe and effective activities in the ever growing and interconnected world.

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